

GEORGIA'S TOURIST AND GEOGRAPHICAL RESOURCES

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ABSTRACT

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Tourism is developing more and more widely every year and goes beyond the borders of many countries. Every developing country is trying to pay significant attention to local resources, which are very important in terms of tourism. Every year the number of travelers in the world is increasing, who escape the chaotic and rhythmic everyday life and try to spend their holidays in a calm and ecologically clean environment. "I am Georgian and therefore I am European" - this is how one of my country's political leaders introduced himself to the world years ago. I would like you to travel with me and introduce you to my country, Georgia, which is located at the crossroads of Asia and Europe and is located between the Black and Caspian Seas. It is distinguished by its beautiful landscape and climatic diversity. Due to its geographical location, the country has many natural and recreational resources, and these resources are represented by resorts and resort areas. In the article, I will try to make a brief overview of all the tourist destinations that are implemented in the country. Georgia has gone through many stages of historical development and today it is already an established state.

KEYWORDS: Georgia, Georgian script, Caucasus, peaks, Georgian folk song, folk instruments, tourist resources

INTRODUCTION

Discussion: Georgia is a country where the fact of human life since ancient times is confirmed by archaeological excavations conducted in the town of Dmanisi, where the fragments of a human skeleton discovered are the oldest in all of Eurasia, whose age is 1,800,000 years. This very important discovery made a significant contribution to the understanding of evolution in Georgia, and according to new research, the oldest man came not from Africa, but from Georgia. Therefore, scientists confirm that the first Europeans set foot on the territory of Georgia.

Georgian script is one of the oldest and is among the 14 scripts in the world. On November 30, 2016, the Georgian alphabet was included in the UNESCO Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. There is no exact source about the introduction of

the Georgian script. Georgian script is one of the most complete scripts in the world. Each sound of the Georgian language has its own letter-symbol in the alphabet. Georgian is pronounced the same way it is written, and it is written the same way it is pronounced. Georgian writing has gone through a long, centuries-long path of development. Over time, as a result of transformation, three graphic types of Georgian writing were created: Asomtavruli or Mrgvlovani; Nuskhuri and Mkhedruli. Until the beginning of the 19th century, all three types of Georgian writing were in use. Gradually, as a result of the establishment of printing, the Georgian Mkhedruli writing gained dominance and became the only Georgian writing.

The country is bordered to the west by the Black Sea, whose coastline is 310 kilometers long. It is one of the most important natural formations for the general geographical location of the country, a resource potential, a recreational zone, and the main artery of external communications. The shores are slightly indented, therefore it is a convenient water area for navigation. In addition, it has a great influence on the formation of the climate of Georgia. There are many resorts on the Black Sea coast that host many local and foreign visitors every year.

Due to the geographical, landscape and climatic diversity, the country has many ecotourism resources. Forests are an important ecotourism resource. A significant part of the territory of Georgia is covered with forests, which are a natural resource of particular value for the country and also contribute to ecological, social and economic development. The total area of forests in Georgia is 2,767,300 hectares, which covers approximately 40% of the entire country's territory. Ecotourism resources - national parks, protected areas, reserves, reserves and natural monuments - are abundant in the country, where endemic species of plants and animals are collected and protected. These resources provide an opportunity for the successful development of ecotourism in the country. It is also worth noting that birdwatching, one of the forms of ecotourism, is successfully implemented in the Kolkheta National Park on the Black Sea coast, where many amateurs and scientists-researchers are involved.

The territory of Georgia is naturally divided into two parts by the Likhi or Trialeti mountain range into Western and Eastern Georgia. The range also acts as a climate divider. Therefore, the climate of Western and Eastern Georgia is very different. Western Georgia has a more humid and humid climate than Eastern Georgia. This humidity is due to the influence of the Black Sea. As for Eastern Georgia, it has a drier climate and in some regions there is even a desert.

The Great Caucasus Mountain System borders the north of the country, which determines the climate, character and geopolitics of the region. It stretches between two seas and is known for its snow-capped peaks. Among them, the highest peak is Shkhara, which is 5203 meters high. There is also Tetnudi, which is 4852 meters high, and the two-headed peak Ushba, which always amazes visitors with its unique beauty. The height of its southern peak is 4700 meters, while the northern one is 10 meters lower. The 5054-meter-high glacier is also attractive to climbers and tourists. Covered with subalpine meadows and eternal glaciers, it plays not only a tourist but also a cultural role.

Diversity. There are a total of twelve regions on the territory of the country, which are distinguished by their traditions, gastronomic and ethnographic diversity.

Due to their geographical location, the mountain region has been an important refuge for the population for centuries. Therefore, traditions were formed and preserved in the mountains.

Over time, due to the settlement of a significant part of the population in the plains, the population of the mountain region has significantly decreased. However, today the mountain has not lost its important values, and those old traditions that almost no longer exist among the population of the plains have been preserved.

Ancient residential towers have survived in the mountains to this day. Svan and Tusheti towers, which are protected and represent cultural heritage monuments. Today, such towers house museums that are of great interest to foreign tourists. Ancient traditions have survived in the mountain regions, and locals are selflessly fighting to preserve these traditions. They also try to revive and introduce old forgotten traditions to the public. The inhabitants of the mountain region have their own customs, dialect, and gastronomy that are unique to the region.

The lowland regions are also distinguished by their diversity, with diverse gastronomy, cultural-historical, eco- and agro-tourism monuments that are characteristic of only one specific region and are authentic. Georgian culture has been distinguished by its traditions and its own characteristics since ancient times, which Georgians have always been proud of.

We must definitely touch on Georgian folk traditional singing - polyphony. Based on archaeological excavations and written sources, we can assume that the beginning of the musical culture of the Georgian nation begins about three millennia ago. It should be noted that Georgian folk songs have been characterized by polyphony since time immemorial. Polyphony, or polyphony, is considered a unique phenomenon, and few peoples of the world can boast of such richness. Georgian polyphony is also completely special, different and diverse among them. Every corner of Georgia has its own musical dialect.

Georgian folk songs represent the customs and lifestyle of our ancestors. Thus, Georgian folk songs also have historical significance. Traces of ancient beliefs, which reflect the mythological beliefs of the Georgians, have survived in Georgia to this day.[1]

For centuries, the Georgian people, along with national songs, created and developed national musical instruments, which they used both in times of joy and in times of trouble. Music was an integral part of the spiritual life of the Georgian people. Obviously, this led to the development of various types of musical instruments and a high culture of their use. Over time, in accordance with musical thinking, the instruments were refined and developed.[1]

Eastern Georgia is a very fertile and powerful region. This region is famous for its vine culture. The culture of growing and caring for vines has been known in Georgia since ancient times. Georgia is an ancient center of vine culture, which is confirmed by historical, archaeological, ethnographic materials, as well as literary monuments. Georgia has been a sphere of interest for foreigners since time immemorial. Ancient culture, historical past, location, faith, identity, folklore, table, hospitality were the attributes that so attracted many prominent researchers, historians, scientists and enthusiastic people who came to Georgia. Georgia is the homeland of the vine and the cradle of wine. This is historically confirmed. Georgia is the only country in the world where wine is made only from Georgian aboriginal grape varieties and the only technology of making wine in the Kakhetian way, in qvevri, is preserved. [2]

The history of wine is inseparable from the history of mankind. It is a cultural achievement and one of the important factors of public life. Therefore, perceiving it as a simple drink is incomplete. In the Georgian Christian tradition, wine is not only a source of joy, life and peace. Good wine, like a person, has its own homeland. It forever absorbs the aroma of its

native land. Georgian wines and alcoholic beverages are characterized by unique, original, aromatic properties and are adorned with the seal of national identity.

Winemaking has been widely developed in Georgia since ancient times. The Kakheti region was especially distinguished in this regard.

Viticulture and winemaking are the oldest and most important branches of Georgian agriculture. The history of vine culture is closely connected with the history of the Georgian nation. The creative nature of our nation and special love for vines and wine were expressed in Georgian culture, traditional customs, architecture, painting, poetry, singing and other fields. With the development of these forms of farming, the country has significant potential in terms of agrotourism development. Local winemakers create agrotourism products within their own farms, which are very attractive and interesting for incoming tourists. Tourists have the opportunity to participate in the profession of grape picking and pressing. Also in wine tasting and the process of preparing traditional dishes, which is a kind of gastronomic adventure. The grape picking process is a kind of spectacle that leaves an indelible mark in the memory of tourists. This is the best way to develop wine tourism and gastronomic tourism, for which the country really has prospects.[2]

I must definitely touch on the recreational resources that are quite abundant in the country. More than 730 types of mineral water are extracted in Georgia, which are used for balneological purposes and for industrial bottling. The healing waters of Georgia differ significantly in their chemical composition and therapeutic properties. These waters are rich in various minerals and gases, each of which has different healing properties. The effective use and development of the healing waters of Georgia makes a great contribution to improving the health of the population and the tourism sector.

Conclusion: In this article, I briefly conveyed the important issues through which I tried to introduce my country - Georgia to the general public. However, one article is not enough to convey the great potential that my country has. Tourism is successful at all times of the year, because due to its geographical location, all the resources that develop many types of tourism are concentrated here. [3]

Visit Georgia, see its beautiful environment, breathtaking nature and taste the cold mountain springs and unique flavors of Georgian traditional cuisine, which have no analogues in the world.

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